

Inclusion4Schools

D3.1 Knowledge Sharing Platforms for Schools at National Level

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Scope

The online platform is created for the purpose of sharing the pedagogical experiences of schools with majority underprivileged students. Interaction between these schools makes it possible to exchange locally developed techniques and methods (good practices or transformative practices) which are successful in improving the students' educational progress. The online platform offers opportunity for informal discussions, creating partnerships and networks as well as sharing case studies and good practices.

Revisions

Version	date	comments	author name and position (author, Task leader, WP leader, PCO, other)
_v1	28-03-2022	first version	György Mészáros (WJLF), Kornél Varga (WJLF)
_v2	31-03-2022	second version corrections and revision	Zsuzsanna Hanna Bíró PCO

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Table of Contents

- 1. Description of the portal** **5**
 - a) Rationale and general concept 5
 - b) Unique features of the portal 5
 - c) Functionality 7
- 2. Technical presentation** **8**
 - a) Technical parameters 8
 - b) Built in translation 8
 - c) Registration and user rights 8
 - d) Data managed by the Portal 8
 - e) Good practices 9
 - f) Forums 9
 - g) Network of Institutions 9
 - h) Adaption 9
- 3. Portal development process** **10**
 - a) Procurement 10
 - b) Development 11
- 4. Annexes** **12**
 - a) Profile template 12
 - i. Individual user: 12
 - ii. Organization/institution template 12
 - b) Institution (self-)evaluation questionnaire 14
 - i. Introduction 14
 - c) Good or transformative practice template 26
 - i. Introduction 26

Inclusion4Schools Project Summary

The emerging European context is to a large extent characterized by widening and deepening inequalities, the crisis of democracy, and the disintegration of communities. It is especially the case in the Central-Eastern European semiperipheral, post-socialist context, where there is a growing tendency of rearticulating authoritarian, nationalist, neoconservative discourses, which are increasingly infiltrating the political landscape within and beyond Europe. This „retrotopia“ is conducive to the hegemonic production of an imaginary social homogeneity, which consequently stirs up reactionary xenophobia, fear, and hatred through the construction of external intruders (e.g. the migrant) and enemies within (e.g. the Roma). Such a milieu steeped in fear tears up old wounds and produces new divisions as well, hence the construction of new walls – symbolically, as well as physically. Since the leitmotif of this programme is primarily educational, the proposed action targets such (imaginary, symbolic, and real) walls of exclusion which are intended to segregate children (based on class, ethnicity, gender, etc.), which are meant to divide and alienate the local communities to which those children nonetheless belong, thus actively (re)producing inequalities. **In contrast to the power-relations of exclusion, the culture of silence, and the reproduction of unjust structures, the project aims to foster and promote pedagogical relations of inclusion, a culture of dialogue, and the transformation of unjust structures through education.** Running in parallel to the research and innovation actions the central objectives of the proposed action are

- (1) to support and coordinate community schools (as being central to the constitution and maintenance of cohesive local communities) and their respective communities of practice, and
- (2) to create a place and culture of sharing (knowledge, praxis, solidarity) between such communities by initiating and coordinating the convergence and synergies of local, regional and transnational communities.

The expected impact of the proposed project is to contribute to the European initiatives and interventions that aim at reversing inequalities. Adopting a mission-oriented, impact-focused approach to address the specific challenges of the call, synergies will be enhanced between the relevant stakeholders through coordinating and supporting the cooperation between teachers, researchers, local communities and other relevant stakeholders (such as policy-makers), in order to generate networks of policy development and to promote the policy uptake of the project.

Partners

Participant No	Participant organisation name	Country
1 (Coordinator)	John Wesley Theological College	Hungary
2	Regional Centre for Information and Scientific Development	Hungary
3	C.E.G.A. Foundation	Bulgaria
4	J. Selye University	Slovakia
5	Oltalom Charity Society	Hungary
6	Albanian National Orphans Association	Albania

1. Description of the portal

a) Rationale and general concept

The portal's fundamental objective is foster the mapping and connecting good practices and institutions. It will give individuals and institutions the opportunity to find and share good practices. Ultimately, the portal aims to facilitate learning between institutions and different actors by building a network among them.

The realisation of this objective fits in with the underlying concept of good or „transformative“ practices developed in the project. The term “transformative practices” is used in the project, rather than established good (best) practices. Behind this unusual terminology lies a critique of the current approach to good practices. The good practices of institutions in the education of disadvantaged children cannot be transferred as a ready-made methodology. They are not recipes or activities that can be copied, but rather practices that have been created in a specific context, in a particular process, and that have worked in some way. It is not only the good practice itself that is important, but also the context and the process of its emergence and implementation. Other institutions or users cannot simply replicate the practice. Learning from the lessons and stories of others, they can create their own practices that are useful in their context and respond to their problems. It is also important that when looking for working practices of others, it is necessary to take a more complex picture of both one's own and the other institution. It can easily happen that a school is looking for an answer to a particular problem and wants to adopt the practice of another institution that has found ways of solving an apparently similar problem. In doing so, however, it may overlook the specific context of that institution, or the fact that, in reality, behind the seemingly similar difficulty lies a completely different deeper problem in the two institutions. It is therefore crucial that institutions look for answers in the light of their own self-assessment.

For this reason, the aim of the portal is not that institutions find quick answers by simply searching, but that they reflect on their own practice in a more complex way of sharing good practice, and thus build networks with other institutions.

b) Unique features of the portal

The portal has some unique features that make it more than just a simple good practice search portal:

- **Diverse user community** – The I4S Portal addresses a wide range of users dealing with disadvantaged pupils: schools, other type of institutions, NGOs, individuals working in this field. Both institutions or organisations and individuals who belong or do not belong to an institution or organisation will be able to register on the portal.
- **International accessibility** – Although the portal was only intended for national use in the first year with the built-in automatic translation function, users will be able to access good (transformative) practices and information on institutions from different countries.

There will be no language barriers to networking, participating in professional forums and sharing knowledge.

- **Uniform terminology** – A professionally structured glossary will assist the search function of the portal. The glossary contains all categories of questionnaires, the questions and the answers to the closed questions. A translation of these categories is available in the glossary will be verified by the national administrator from each country. As these basic categories can only be changed via the central administrator, any changes can be immediately checked by the national administrators. This ensures that the categories remain the same when the language is changed.
- **Community development** – Forums linked to good practices will offer the opportunity to learn more about transformative activities, ask questions, and make contacts and build networks. However, the portal's forum is also suitable for the formation of an international community to solve a particular problem, and for the creation of transformative practices through joint work.
- **Methods to present good practices** – Good practices can be shared by institutions in two ways: by providing their own presentation with images, videos, descriptions and by filling in a template. In the latter, the creators of the practice should provide several aspects that help the reader to have a clear understanding of the context, history and specificities of the practice in order to be adaptable, but also support the institution to think through its own practice along the lines of the aspects provided. The template allows all professionally relevant aspects to be included in the description, the individual presentation of a good practice gives institutions the opportunity to be creative.
- **Matching algorithms** – When preparing the institutional profile, the portal invites each institution to prepare a detailed analysis of its own situation and conditions, with a special focus on the inclusive nature of the school. This easy-to-complete but comprehensive institutional self-assessment questionnaire helps the institution to place itself on a kind of "problem map": what are its strengths and what are the main areas of weakness. The results of the institutional self-assessments, which place the school on a five-point scale for each aspect, can be subjected to a statistical evaluation, the aim being to develop a typology that will allow us to link schools with the same problems using an algorithm.
- **Criteria for institutional self-evaluation** – The portal itself will help participants by linking institutions facing similar problems. The strengths of the institutions will also be clearly visible. The problem areas/dimensions are defined by the self-assessment questionnaire in the Annex. They were developed by consulting international literature and practical guides:
 - o The school as community
 - o Democratic way of working
 - o Teachers' community
 - o Relationship with partners
 - o Embeddedness (in the social context)
 - o Inclusion
 - o Differentiated teaching
 - o Adaptive methodology
 - o Supporting students' achievement
 - o Drop-out prevention
 - o Compliance with rules (discipline)
 - o Educating for everyday life skills

- o Education for social activity
 - o Value transmission
 - o Learning community
- **Visualisation of the contact networks** – The network that is being built around the institutions with the help of the matching algorithms will also be visually represented on the portal (linked institutions, exchanged or shared good practices, trials and adaptations of the institution's transformative practices). However, the development of algorithms and visualisation will not take place until 2023, as we need data for this development work and it will take a year to have the number of registered users needed to further develop the portal.
 - **Easy adaptability of the portal structures** – In the first development phase (September 2022 to March 2023), in addition to the basic functionalities of the portal, we focused on making the structure easily customizable. Therefore, four admin levels allow changes to the structural elements of the portal:
 - at the super admin level, only the developer can modify the systemic elements of the portal (e.g., design, main functions, pages, editing interfaces, etc.);
 - at the central admin level, everything that is content can be changed (questions, categories in the glossary, descriptions, instructions for questionnaires, etc.) and access can be set (e.g., who can be in charge for national admins);
 - national administrators check and correct the translation of the terms in the glossary;
 - school administrators are responsible for uploading the school profile presentation and filling in the central template questionnaire. They have also right to moderate all materials uploaded by teachers of the school.

c) Functionality

The portal will be accessible to non-registered users, who will be able to search the public information on institutions and good practices. Registered users will have access to the full functionality of the website: create your own profile page; search by all the information provided by the institutions; post comments in forums; present new good practices etc.

There will be basically two types of registration:

- institutional registration: an authorised person registers on behalf of the institution. To do this, an institutional profile must be completed, which then contains different questions and data for different types of institutions.
- individual registration: this can be linked to the institutional registration if the user is a member of that institution.

The creation of the profile is facilitated by a questionnaire linked to the profile. Then, in the case of institutional registration, the user has to fill in the institutional self-assessment questionnaire, which gives an idea of his/her strengths and weaknesses in the given professional areas.

Institutions and individuals can also upload good practices using the template, which they can supplement with their own presentation based on images and text. These can be searched and forums can be created for each good practice.

2. Technical presentation

a) Technical parameters

The client program runs in a browser. It was developed in the React programming environment (which is used by Facebook). The server background is a MySQL database. The server provider is RackForest Ltd. (H-1132 Budapest, Victor Hugo str. 11.). Both the client and server programs are custom developments, for which the developers grant unlimited usage rights. The technologies used are free of charge, there are no license fees.

b) Built in translation

The program interface is working in five languages. Uploaded materials can be translated either automatically or by request. DeepL and Google Translate are used for translations. The translated questionnaire texts can be manually proofread and corrected. For uploaded data there is no manual correction.

c) Registration and user rights

At personal registration private or administrator status can be chosen. The later will be authorized by an existing administrator.

Private persons may connect to a school but this is not compulsory. Individuals can also create their own profile page and upload good practices to the portal, but we do not want to widen this user base in the first year, as the aim is to include as many segregated schools as possible in the knowledge sharing activity in WP3.

A policy on user rights and obligations is being drafted with the help of legal experts and will be available to read via the portal. All users must accept it when registering on the portal.

d) Data managed by the Portal

The data of the portal are grouped in four catalogues: good practices, forums, school profiles and personal profiles. You can choose one of these on the opening page. The list of participant people is only visible to registered users, the other three catalogues are also available to guest users.

Providing data is voluntary for all catalogues, and in the profile data you can also set what can be displayed to non-registered audiences. As we want to link users and good practices to each other by analysing questionnaires and profile data, these data will be stored in a large database, but we this database will contain a user code instead of the name and other identifying information of the user.

The users are responsible for the legality and correctness of the data, documents, images, etc. uploaded to the portal, as it will set in the policy on user rights and obligations.

e) Good practices

Only registered users can upload good practices. The data for good practices consists of two parts (similarly as school data):

- responses to the centrally created questionnaire, and
- a freely compiled presentation consisting of slides (similar to a PowerPoint presentation).

The catalogue contains the questionnaire answers and the first slide of the presentation. These can be searched for keywords. You can view the selected good practice in detail. The uploader of the good practice can edit the data afterwards.

The presentation slide consists of a title, formatted text, image or video and tags. You can search in the tag cloud. Files can be attached to a slide.

f) Forums

Registered users can start a forum or join an existing forum. The forum post has the same form as a presentation slide. Besides posts members can also write comments and answers.

A forum can be linked to a good practice in two ways:

- discuss a subject in form of a preparation workshop which results in a good practice.
- discuss the application and adaption experiences of an uploaded good practice.

g) Network of Institutions

The connection of forums to good practices makes possible to filter those institutions and persons who are working on the same subject. The adaptations of good practices are specially marked, so you can follow the experiences of adaptations.

h) Adaption

There was an important aspect at the design of the portal that it should be easily adaptable to changing circumstances. Adaption has several aspects:

- The compact data structure of the portal provides not only an easy usage but also an efficient and flexible communication. Slides can be copied from one good practice to another which makes it easy to adapt good practices to local circumstances.
- As the forum post has the same slide format, there is an easy data transfer among forums and good practices. This supports final formulation of a good practice after a discussion process in a forum.

- There is no language barrier thanks to automatic translation: participants can follow a forum on their mother language, independently from the language the post was written in.
- In the first phase the project concentrates on schools. But later new types of institutions will join. A kindergarten or university needs definitely different questionnaire than a school. Even good practices can vary on a broad scale. Conditional questions make possible to offer different questions based on profile data, e.g., the type of institution.
- The questionnaire editor is an important tool of this adaption process. The central administrators of the project can modify and extend the questionnaires without programming assistance.

3. Portal development process

a) Procurement

None of the partners had the necessary technical knowledge and capacity to develop the portal, a service provider had to be involved.

Based on previous experience and the nature of the task, the coordinator followed their usual inner procurement rules and procedures.

The contracting party was the John Wesley Theological College, the coordinator of the project.

Technical specifications were elaborated by the consortium members with detailed description of the platform's functions, structure, expectations towards developers and the deadlines for the subtasks.

These technical specifications and the call for offers were sent out via e-mail, on 25 August 2021. Deadline for submission of offers was 3 September 2021. There were three companies invited to the place their offers:

- Viola Software Bt.
- DYB Group Ltd.
- webAND Ltd.

Offers:

1. Viola Software Bt., Received on 2 September 2021
2. webAND Ltd. did not send any offers.
3. DYB Group Ltd. sent an e-mail on 3 September 2021 stating that they are unable to submit an offer because they are unable to complete the work within the requested timeframe

In case of Viola Software Bt. the offer was complete and met the requested criteria: the references were attached, a declaration was provided regarding the grounds for exclusion, the offer meet the formal criteria.

Price offered:

7.800.000 (seven million eight hundred thousand) HUF + VAT, in the following instalments:

30-30-30% of the total price for the first three sub-periods, the remaining 10% after the closing date of 31 December 2022.

Decision was taken by an evaluation committee, consisting of the PCO Ms Zsuzsanna Hanna Biró, the chief financial officer of the College, Mr István Ónodi and countersigned by WP7 manager Barbara Szuromi. The committee accepted the offer submitted by Viola Software Bt. It was noted that only one offer was received in response to the invitation.

b) Development

After contracting the chosen company, the development process has started based on the specification used in the selection process in September 2021.

In the development of the portal, Zsuzsanna Hanna Biró and György Mészáros were involved as researchers, certain content elements (questionnaires, templates) have already been completed in WP1 Task 1.1, their integration and adaptation in the portal is still ongoing based on the professional feedback of researchers, teachers.

The first version of the portal was presented by the head of the development company, Mr Kornél Varga, at our interim consortium meeting on 26 October 2021, where we discussed a number of issues to continue the development work.

The basic structure and the main elements of the portal were established by the beginning of 2022, which was presented to the consortium by the developers at our interim status update meeting on 22 February 2022.

The platform was presented by Mr Varga and Mr Mészáros with all the functionalities: how a person or a school can create their own profile, the self-assessment questionnaires, the good practices and the forum where discussions can take place. They presented the various structures behind the platform: the glossary of terms, the automatic built-in translations and how these can be used as filters for searches.

Partners could discuss further relevant issues, e.g., the motivation of the schools to provide more information, the various systems of assistance to use, communication of the platform and various legal issues.

In the course of March the portal has been tested by colleagues of the consortium, and they suggested adjustments and corrections to questionnaires and to finalise design.

Final step of the process is to link the language varieties of the platform to the project website, each language variety to the corresponding language variety of the website, and to offer links.

The platform will be launched in early April 2022, it will be offered to schools that have participated in WP1 first. In the first year, schools will learn about the portal on an invitation basis and start using it with the assistance of the project staff.

By autumn 2022, we aim to have at least a quarter of segregated schools registered in each country. To help schools share good practices, we also support schools with online workshops and a series of crowdsourcing and knowledge sharing events.

This introduction will be parallel in the four countries, Further participants are planned to reach via extended and targeted media campaigns.

4. Annexes

a) Profile template

i. Individual user:

Please, fill in the following data for registration.

Username
First name
Surname
Postal code
Country
Email address
Institution (choice from the list of registered institutions)
Position (choice from a list: leader, administrator, teacher etc.)

If the institution, to which the user is affiliated, not registered yet. New users have to fill in the information required for institutions.

ii. Organization/institution template

(At the moment, we will accept schools as organizations. Thus, this is only the registration form for schools. We will develop another template for other types of institutions/organisations later).

Data of the representative of the school (who make the registration)	Please, fill in the following data regarding the person who represents the school and make this registration.
Full name	
Email	
Role in the school	
Organisation details	Please, fill in the following data regarding the your school.
The official, full name of the school	
Official postal address	
Organisation phone number	
Website	
Facebook	
Twitter	
Instagram	
other contact	
School details	
Maintained by	must be given in text
Number of students	number must be given
Number of teachers	number must be given
Number of disadvantaged students	number must be given

Type of the school	
Kindergarten	
Primary/lower secondary school	
Institution providing vocational training	
Secondary school/gymnasium: non-vocational education institution offering a final exam (for example maturity)	
Special education institution	
College-university	

b) Institution (self-)evaluation questionnaire

i. Introduction

The following questionnaire is designed to help your institution's self-evaluation. Its purpose is to give you an idea of the main aspects in which your institution is stronger and weaker in helping disadvantaged pupils. The questionnaire results will help you see in which areas your institution is best able to help others and where it needs to improve.

The areas are not limited to specific activities for disadvantaged pupils but ask about the broader context of their education and the institution's organisational culture. Indeed, sharing initiatives and good practices on the website will be effective if we do not simply share activities but also consider their context.

Please, answer the following questions to the best of your knowledge. The results obtained do not fully describe the characteristics and nature of your school but can be used as a basis for self-reflection and improvement. You may also ask other members of the institution about the characteristics. The questionnaire can also be used for internal reflection and institutional development purposes if discussed with the different actors.

Please indicate, on a scale of 1 to 8, the extent to which each of the following criteria is characteristic of your institution.

<u>Area</u>	<u>Criteria</u>
The school as community	
1 2 3 4 5	the school is characterized by frequent events, social occasions
1 2 3 4 5	there is a positive climate, positive relations with each other
1 2 3 4 5	school management is accessible, in constant contact with other actors
1 2 3 4 5	school stakeholders show solidarity with each other
1 2 3 4 5	parents are actively involved in school life
1 2 3 4 5	teachers are active participants and shape the school community
1 2 3 4 5	students are actively involved in the school community
Democratic way of working	
1 2 3 4 5	the teaching staff is actively involved in the decision-making process
1 2 3 4 5	students are actively involved in the decision-making process
1 2 3 4 5	the institution has a student council and it has active role in decision-making
1 2 3 4 5	parents are involved in the decision-making process
1 2 3 4 5	the school community regularly organise forums and joint decision-making events

Teachers' community	
1 2 3 4 5	the teaching staff is cohesive
1 2 3 4 5	teachers support each other
1 2 3 4 5	low turnover of teachers, who typically stay for several years
1 2 3 4 5	the institution has a common set of values
1 2 3 4 5	the school has a consistent, united human and pedagogical approach
Relationship with partners	
1 2 3 4 5	the institution has an active relationship with the local government
1 2 3 4 5	active links with NGOs
1 2 3 4 5	active relationship with churches
1 2 3 4 5	active links with cultural institutions
1 2 3 4 5	active links with social institutions
1 2 3 4 5	active relations with other types of institutions (itt meg kellene tudni adnia egy szöveges válaszban, hogy milyen típusúak ezek)
Embeddedness	
1 2 3 4 5	the school is linked to local communities which determine its composition

1 2 3 4 5	the school has links with other, more distant communities (e.g. nationalities, religious communities) that are significant for the pupils
1 2 3 4 5	the school has active connections to pupils' families
1 2 3 4 5	the school is involved in the community(ies) of pupils and their families (programmes, meetings, active activities, outreach activities)
1 2 3 4 5	the school provides a wide range of services to the local and/or wider community (specific services listed separately below)
Inclusion	
1 2 3 4 5	the proportion of pupils with special educational needs and disadvantaged pupils is adequate (10% is the optimum, the highest score)
1 2 3 4 5	the percentage of SEN pupils is accurate.
1 2 3 4 5	exact percentage of disadvantaged pupils
1 2 3 4 5	the percentage of teachers who fall into the same minority category(ies) as the pupils are relevant (this could be disabled, ethnic, religious or other minorities)
1 2 3 4 5	teachers have a positive attitude towards the presence and teaching of pupils with disabilities or SEN
1 2 3 4 5	teachers are prepared to teach children with different needs
1 2 3 4 5	school premises take into account the diversity of pupils and their different needs
1 2 3 4 5	the school time structure takes into account the diversity of pupils and their different needs

1 2 3 4 5	the school accommodates and provides opportunities for pupils who are not succeeding elsewhere
Differentiated teaching	
1 2 3 4 5	the school uses a differentiated methodology
1 2 3 4 5	the school has individual development programmes
1 2 3 4 5	pupil pairs are in place
1 2 3 4 5	there are sufficient teaching assistants/students in the school
1 2 3 4 5	there are development teachers and they collaborate with the teaching staff
1 2 3 4 5	the school has a well functioning talent management programme
1 2 3 4 5	the school's talent management programme is able to reach a wide range of pupils with different talents, using a diverse approach to talent
Adaptive methodology	
1 2 3 4 5	the school tries out and applies innovative methods
1 2 3 4 5	teachers often use cooperative or group work methods.
1 2 3 4 5	the school often uses project-based teaching methods.
1 2 3 4 5	teachers use a variety of methodologies in lessons/activities
1 2 3 4 5	teachers are open to trying out new methods
1 2 3 4 5	teachers adapt to pupils' knowledge, competences and specificities

1 2 3 4 5	in addition to the transmission of knowledge, the development of competences is also a feature of the institution.
1 2 3 4 5	teachers and the institution value and use the knowledge that children bring from home and from their own world (family knowledge, popular culture, subcultures)
1 2 3 4 5	teachers seek to see and evaluate pupils on the basis of their individual characteristics beyond their categories
Supporting students' achievement	
1 2 3 4 5	teachers use a wide range of assessment methods in differentiated ways (textual, numerical, feedback, formative, summative, diagnostic)
1 2 3 4 5	creative and innovative forms of assessment (self-assessment, peer assessment, portfolio, etc.)
1 2 3 4 5	individual learning pace for pupils is used
1 2 3 4 5	the school organises a wide range of internal competitions for pupils
1 2 3 4 5	the school and teachers have a varied motivational toolbox
Drop-out prevention	
1 2 3 4 5	the school uses the family visit method
1 2 3 4 5	the school cooperates with family support organisations.
1 2 3 4 5	pupils receive career guidance according to their age.
1 2 3 4 5	the school is in contact with local or regional employers

1 2 3 4 5	the institution also exploits pupils' competences not directly related to learning (organisational skills, technical skills, artistic skills, etc.), which can increase their attachment to the school.
Compliance with rules	
1 2 3 4 5	the institution is characterised by the joint creation of rules with the relevant actors (students, teachers, etc.).
1 2 3 4 5	the institution and its subdivisions have a transparent set of rules.
1 2 3 4 5	the system of rules is predictable and accessible
1 2 3 4 5	rules apply to all
1 2 3 4 5	the application of the rules takes into account the specific circumstances of the institution
1 2 3 4 5	sanctions are imposed in accordance with the rules, are not excessive and promote the development of pupils and teachers.
1 2 3 4 5	there is a high level of compliance and discipline of pupils and teachers
Everyday life skills	
1 2 3 4 5	the school also teaches competences for everyday life.
1 2 3 4 5	the school has open days for parents and other stakeholders.
1 2 3 4 5	parents' competences and knowledge are also valued, and parents are involved in knowledge transfer in the school (workshops, use of parents' knowledge, parents' circle, parents' lectures)

1 2 3 4 5	pupils has the opportunity to be challenged in a wide range of real-life situations outside the classroom (organising, volunteering, getting involved in organisations, fieldwork, contact with employers, etc.)
Education for social activity	
1 2 3 4 5	citizenship education is a key focus of the institution, giving students the tools to assert their rights and fight for social change.
1 2 3 4 5	education for sustainability is present in the daily life of the school and in classroom teaching
1 2 3 4 5	the institution promotes various forms of social responsibility for students and teachers (service, volunteering, participation in programmes)
1 2 3 4 5	pupils may participate in community service and receive appropriate pedagogical support in carrying out this service
Value transmission	
1 2 3 4 5	the school is characterised by the transmission of values, character formation beyond instruction
1 2 3 4 5	there are shared rituals that are not rigid but help to engage participants.
1 2 3 4 5	the school develops, along with its differences, some kind of community of values in the institution
1 2 3 4 5	teachers use several indirect character education methods that involve pupils
1 2 3 4 5	the institution has a tradition of values

Learning community	
1 2 3 4 5	the institution organises and provides in-service training for teachers.
1 2 3 4 5	the institution provides working time allowances for teachers in longer training courses
1 2 3 4 5	the institution offers the possibility of building individual career paths
1 2 3 4 5	the institution builds an internal learning community alongside individual training.
1 2 3 4 5	organised joint problem-solving sessions for teachers (staff, workshops, etc.)
1 2 3 4 5	the institution also organises internal training
1 2 3 4 5	teachers participate in joint development activities (teaching materials, methods, etc.)
1 2 3 4 5	other school actors (staff, parents, students, partners) are involved in the learning community, in concentric circles: joint workshops, facilitating shared reflection.
1 2 3 4 5	teachers participate in in-house and external visits
1 2 3 4 5	teachers and their communities have ongoing opportunities for self-evaluation.
1 2 3 4 5	feedback and constructive evaluation of teachers' work by the management
Please indicate whether you have or not the following services, and if the respective service is open to the public (freely or not).	
Services	

studytime	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ we don't have it ○ we have it: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ only for the members/families of the institution ○ also for the public: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ freely ▪ for money
computer room	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ we don't have it ○ we have it: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ only for the members/families of the institution ○ also for the public: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ freely ▪ for money
gym	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ we don't have it ○ we have it: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ only for the members/families of the institution ○ also for the public: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ freely ▪ for money
swimming pool	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ we don't have it ○ we have it: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ only for the members/families of the institution ○ also for the public: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ freely ▪ for money
restaurant	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ we don't have it ○ we have it: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ only for the members/families of the institution ○ also for the public: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ freely ▪ for money

snack bar	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ we don't have it ○ we have it: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ only for the members/families of the institution ○ also for the public: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ freely ▪ for money
sports fields	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ we don't have it ○ we have it: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ only for the members/families of the institution ○ also for the public: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ freely ▪ for money
parents' club	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ we don't have it ○ we have it: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ only for the members/families of the institution ○ also for the public: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ freely ▪ for money
adult education (courses) for parents	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ we don't have it ○ we have it: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ only for the members/families of the institution ○ also for the public: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ freely ▪ for money
baby room	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ we don't have it ○ we have it: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ only for the members/families of the institution ○ also for the public: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ freely ▪ for money

clothes collection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ we don't have it ○ we have it: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ only for the members/families of the institution ○ also for the public: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ freely ▪ for money
collecting books	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ we don't have it ○ we have it: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ only for the members/families of the institution ○ also for the public: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ freely ▪ for money
collecting toys	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ we don't have it ○ we have it: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ only for the members/families of the institution ○ also for the public: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ freely ▪ for money
fundraising for the school	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ we don't have it ○ we have it: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ only for the members/families of the institution ○ also for the public: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ freely ▪ for money
fundraising for those in need	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ we don't have it ○ we have it: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ only for the members/families of the institution ○ also for the public: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ freely ▪ for money

holiday programmes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ we don't have it ○ we have it: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ only for the members/families of the institution ○ also for the public: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ freely ▪ for money
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c) Good or transformative practice template

i. Introduction

Good practices developed by an institution are best practices, solutions or, in other cases, experiments that help the institution to find appropriate responses to the problems and challenges it faces. In a broader sense, good practices are not only solutions that have been proven by measurement or scientific research, but also innovations that are born out of professionals' everyday experience and knowledge. Such practices can be useful for other organisations to learn from and adapt to find solutions to their own (similar) problems.

The transfer of good practices has become a key activity in education in recent decades. However, alongside the benefits of peer learning, there are also pitfalls. On the one hand, practices may be seen by other institutions as easy solutions or recipe, ignoring the process and context in which the activity was born and could work. On the other hand, in the process of adaptation, they may forget that they have to adapt to their own circumstances a process that has been tried and tested elsewhere. The point is often not the adaptation itself, but the developmental learning process that the organisation goes through in developing its own practices. This is the guarantee of long-term change.

Accordingly, in this questionnaire, we ask the institution not only to describe briefly its own good practice, but also to place it in its own context, to describe briefly the history of its development and implementation, and to answer a few more questions: on the practice's defining values, objectives, nature, impact, its links with inclusion, and its conditions. For the project developing the website, an important dimension is the transformation and positive change in the wider and narrower social environment, institutions and learners. This aspect is also addressed in the questionnaire, indicating that good practice in this sense also means transformative practice. The answers to the questions will help other users to find the most appropriate examples and lessons to learn in designing their own paths and solutions. The

institution has the possibility to provide different services to interested users to help there adaptation.

Mutual learning does not mean that one institution transfers knowledge to another, but is always a reciprocal process. Even if one institution adopts and applies a specific good practice. In this case, the feedback and dialogue around the practice also provides lessons for the institution offering it.

If the practice is still in its initial, pilot phase, not all questions need to be answered and the practice still can be shared. However, it is crucial to fill in further details later to make the activity more adaptable.

Author/user	
The person/institution which has created or adapted the practice and is sharing it now*	
Source	
Who are the original developers (if different from the actual user)?	
History of the adaptation: how was it discovered; why was it adopted?	
History of the adaptation: when did it start, how did it happen?	
Development History	
What was the initial problem to which the practice was born? (3-10 lines)*	
Describe how the exercise was developed (max. 10 lines).	
Describe, if relevant, how you applied it and what your experience was (max. 10. lines).	

Context	
How can the group for whom the practice has been developed be identified? (What is the target group of the practice?)*	
What kind of environment do they live in?	
What specific characteristics do they have?	
What challenges do they face?	
How would you describe the social environment of your institution? What are the specific characteristics of your institution that have been important in developing and implementing the good practice or are essential to understanding it?	

Values	
What are the values on which the practice is based?	
What values does the practice transmit to the target group?	

In the next two sections, please choose one or more options per question and make x-s in the cell next to the answer.

Objectives	
What are the general objectives of the practice?*	
community development	
social inclusion	
inclusive education	
community cooperation	
overcoming disadvantages	
talent management	
innovation in teaching methods	
new pedagogical culture	
a new type of institution	
other general objective:	<i>text answer, if relevant:</i>

Educational objectives	
What are the practice's educational objectives, if there are?	
behavioural change	
motivation	
sensitisation	
developing basic skills	
specific skills	
knowledge capture and retrieval	
practice-repetition	
assessment	

learning techniques		
self-assessment		
other educational objective:		<i>text answer, if relevant:</i>
What are the conditions for the practice's implementation?		
age range*		
group size		
types of work		
time required*		
tools*		
preparation		
specific knowledge		
personnel requirements		
Please, describe in detail what is the methodology: the exact steps and the process of the practice*		

Impacts	
Please, list the expected impacts of the practice on the target group according to your experience.*	
Please, list the expected impacts of the practice for the institution using it.	
Please, list the wider impacts (in the context of the institution or target group, or in the wider social context) that you have experienced.	